
Sociocybernetics and action research: Analysis and intervention in complex social problems

Patricia E Almaguer-Kalixto

Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain

Margarita Maass Moreno

CEIICH, UNAM, Mexico

José Antonio Amozurrutia

CEIICH, UNAM, Mexico

Abstract

Participatory action research (PAR) has been used as a methodology for social intervention that combines research enquiry and action in the analysis of and intervention in complex social problems. However, a better systematization of complex social research processes is required to enable reflexivity at a participatory level and second-order observation of the full research system constructed. This article proposes a PAR model using conceptual and methodological elements of sociocybernetics, which is the application of first- and second-order cybernetics and general systems theory to social sciences. The authors see this model as able to reinforce the systematization of PAR, enabling a second-order reflexivity and feedback process through information analysis and communication strategies. The first part of the article explains how sociocybernetics concepts can contribute to this sociological methodology and discusses points of similarity between the two approaches and the basis of the proposed model. The second part addresses an empirical case of PAR developed in the context of the High Atlas in Morocco using the proposed model. By reinforcing a systems perspective, internal and external elements of the research system can be defined better to understand its relevance to optimal

fulfilment of the research purpose. The value that sociocybernetics adds may be the comprehension of processes of change through the assimilation, accommodation and adaptation of the components and limits of the system, the feedback process and other interactions within the system and its environment, in order to analyse how social changes occur in complex settings.

Keywords

Action research, complexity, High Atlas, Imlil-Morocco, interdisciplinary studies, sociocybernetics, social intervention

Introduction

Analysing emerging social processes presents a significant methodological challenge, particularly for sociologists and groups of professional practitioners – such as social workers – focusing on social transformation through organized action. As Abraham and Purkayasta (2012) state, the analysis required for this purpose includes a wide range of knowledge production oriented to community-based participatory research. Most involves various levels of collaboration, participation, effective practice, deliberation and other forms of interaction at multiple levels in different structural settings and via different channels of communication that envision a social science which can lead to social action.

Participatory action research has been widely implemented in addressing social intervention issues ranging from education to rural development, strategies for social change and participatory knowledge (Dick, 2001; Galuppo et al., 2011), and has proved itself a useful methodological framework.¹ However, while it is now a formalized methodology with a vast range of styles and forms of application (Barton et al., 2009), it has been criticized as unorthodox, ideologically biased and methodologically naive (Couto, 1987; Frideres, 1992). We have to acknowledge that weaknesses in the systematization of some studies have led to insufficient empirical evidence to explain social change, and that the level of complexity increases with the integration of heterogeneous participants in a long-term research process.

There is ongoing debate about what constitutes PAR and the basic elements of its methodology. We use Balcazar's PAR taxonomy (2003) to underline its principal characteristics: the degree of control that individuals have over the action research process; the degree of collaboration between external professional researchers and members of the local community over decision-making processes; the level of community participants and external researchers' involvement in the research process; and the potential social change produced by and within the research project that can be derived from it. But how can we define a research system from these factors?

Efforts to define systemic action research approaches have been made engaging open-systems thinking and reflective enquiry (Burke, 2006; Burns, 2007; Herrscher, 2006); methodological designs based on soft systems methodologies (Bell and Morse, 2010; Hanafizadeh and Rojin, 2011; Rodríguez-Ulloa et al., 2005); and even computer simulation (Rosmulder et al., 2011). Indeed, there is recognition of the influence of systemic

thinking based on action research and particularly the use of Lewin, Bateson and Luhmann's theories (Barton et al., 2009; Dick, 2011; Flood, 2010; Hawkins, 2004; Lara-Rosano, 2018). This, however, has not reached a generalized methodological reflection in practice that allows integration of the participants' reflexivity and yet explains the path of actions taken, for second-order observation.

Making the case for sociocybernetics concepts

As discussed in articles in the present *Current Sociology* monograph issue, the roots and development of sociocybernetics bring together a plurality of areas of knowledge.² Sociocybernetics addresses the challenges of applying analysis to complex social problems which are understood as situations and processes that, for optimal understanding, can barely be classified by their correspondence with a particular discipline inasmuch as the conceptualization of their elements cannot be separated or studied in isolation, as they are interdefined (García, 2006). This is a challenge that most disciplines face and which is leading to the development of rigorous interdisciplinary research processes. In this section we explain how a systemic view of PAR is viable, and how sociocybernetics concepts can contribute to strengthening such methodology.

Most of the literature based on systems theory and cybernetics agrees that a system is arbitrarily defined, seeking a specific purpose that defines internal (element/components, subsystems, relationships) and external (contextual) elements. Nonetheless, there is agreement of some essential characteristics: a system's parts must all be present for the system to carry out its purpose optimally; a system's parts must be arranged in a specific way for it to achieve its purpose; systems have specific purposes within larger systems; systems maintain their stability through fluctuations and adjustments; and systems actions include feedback, which is the way the system feeds itself with information and regulates its own actions (Anderson and Johnson, 1997). Systems may be considered complex if they are composed of subsystems whose elements are highly heterogeneous and whose parts cannot be divided to be interdependent with mutual dependencies of their functions; they have processes at different levels that are linked to one another by structural relationships that can even overlap; and they maintain a density of relationships both inside and outside the limits of the system, which is defined by an operational closure (García, 2006).

Sociocybernetics focuses on open systems in interaction with their observers (Geyer, 1995: 24). The concept of an open system derives largely from the biological philosophy of Von Bertalanffy (1968), applied to systems that involve an exchange of materials with their environment, through inputs and outputs, to produce changes in their components that generate different states. The systemic approach explains these processes through the concepts of feedback and adaptation.

Therefore a fundamental part of the systemic perspective is explaining the limits of the system. Felix Geyer (1995), one of the key proponents of sociocybernetics, proposes that 'the way system boundaries are drawn is observer dependent, time dependent and most importantly also problem dependent' (Geyer, 1995: 9), but does this leave us in a sort of absolute relativism? From a sociocybernetics perspective, the observer is required to take responsibility for the system definition but also for the subsystems – elements or

components that should be especially looked at – and the suprasystem(s), contextual elements and relationships chosen for the analysis. This is fundamental to explicit system definition and delimitation of its internal organization and relationships with elements of the context, particularly in open systems. From a Luhmannian perspective:

A system that can observe may have the capacity to observe itself. To observe itself it has to distinguish itself from everything else, that is from its environment. The recursively interconnected operations of the system draw a boundary and thereby differentiate system and environment. (Luhmann, 1993: 772)

Understanding adaptation is fundamental to understanding and explaining the evolution of social systems. Luhmann (1998: 53–54) refers to it as the ability of systems to ‘adapt to the environment and survive’, clarifying that complex systems must also ‘adapt to their own complexity’. Walter Buckley (1993) sees adaptation as an essential process in the system–environment relationship. It is an operation resulting from the internal organization of the system, from which it manages to respond to contextual irritations by discriminating the interchange of information and energy from the outside to the inside of the system created. This process is done through a ‘mapping’ operation which establishes relations of reciprocal correspondence between the common elements of the system and part of the variety of environmental constraints within the system’s organizational structure. As García (2006: 39) states, ‘no system is given at the starting point of the investigation. The system is not defined, but it is definable. A proper definition can only arise in the course of the investigation itself and for each case in particular.’³ This includes the logics of PAR, which in its first stage requires the definition and delimitation of the system to be studied via participatory approaches.

This article discusses the conceptual and methodological basis of an analytical model for PAR based on sociocybernetics. Second-order observation, as the basis of sociocybernetics, is explicitly formalized in a constructivist epistemology concerned with issues of system delimitation, self-organization through positive and negative feedback, the observer-dependence of knowledge, and circular and elliptical causality, among other key concepts that we review in the following section.

What value does sociocybernetics add to social science? It uses a systemic approach to analyse how social changes occur in complex settings. This requires understanding the processes of change through assimilation, accommodation and adaptation of the components of the process/system under study, its limits, feedback processes and other interactions within the system and its environment. As a paradigm it is compatible with social study methods that prioritize reflexivity, iteration and learning in the research process over methodological individualism. In this way sociocybernetics may provide the conceptual paradigm not only for qualitative (i.e. ethnography, grounded theory, hermeneutics, critical theory) but also mixed methods (i.e. PAR itself), as they benefit from the reflexivity process.

Alverson and Skoldberg (2000: 5) refer to different uses in the literature of ‘reflexivity or reflection which typically draw attention to the complex relationship between processes of knowledge production and the various contexts of such processes as well as the involvement of the knowledge producer. This involves operating on at least two levels in

research work and paying much attention to how one thinks about thinking.’ In sociocybernetics terms this implies acknowledging the system observer, who is therefore always part of the system.

Focus on second-order observation

What is the difference between sociocybernetics and other systemic perspectives, for example general systems theory? Bailey (2006) synthesizes its six main contributions: sociocybernetics is an actor-oriented approach, an aspect not included in other systemic perspectives; it emphasizes change – that is, it seeks to show clearly how changes occur in systems, which requires an understanding of the processes of change or in other words, understanding of the system dynamics; sociocybernetics emphasizes adaptation, change and movement – although it analyses the way in which the negative feedback model returns the system to the status quo, it is also interested in processes of positive feedback;⁴ sociocybernetics has a non-insular approach focused on interaction with not only the environment but also other actors, and is interested in analysing self-controlled processes; and finally, sociocybernetics is a second-order paradigm that emphasizes ‘the subjective character of knowledge dependent on time and the observer. Links exist not only between the components of the observed system, but also between the system and the observer, which is therefore always part of the system’ (Bailey, 2006: 378). This is also addressed by Birrer (1999: 814), who maintains that classical system frameworks fail to reflect how the observer is part of the system observed.

For a better understanding of complex social problems and an efficient quest for their resolution, sociocybernetics relies on the construction of models: a method linking the processing of information with computation assistance and constructivist frameworks. This is because second-order cybernetics (Von Foerster, 1998), as the basis of sociocybernetics, inherits its concern with the resolution of problems from the theory of systems.

From the sociocybernetics perspective, the cognitive observer reconstructs reality by differentiating and distinguishing ‘elements/relationships’ in what s/he has defined as the system (Luhmann, 1998: 44). The emphasis on the observer brings attention to the other key component of sociocybernetics that is useful for an analytical model: the concept of second-order observation. This is one of the key aspects of sociocybernetics from which other sociological frameworks can benefit. Indeed, second-order observation is one of the fundamental elements of its methodology: ‘the observation of the observation process and the reintroduction of information into the research system (feedback) becomes a permanent search and integration task’ (Marcuello, 2006: 10). As Birrer (1999) states, the implication of the second-order observation for the analysis of and intervention in social problems is particularly with respect to the role and responsibility of the systems analyst (the second-order observer).

While PAR emphasizes observation of action produced in the research process, sociocybernetics focuses on observation of the actions and processes within the system analysed – the research itself – and in a further step, the reflection derived from meta-observation of the observation process. Considering PAR an observation system, sociocybernetics enables a second-order observation which observes the research

process which constitutes the observing system itself. In PAR frameworks, this requires one to integrate register and analyse the whole process, which will help make the system learning more accountable.

Focus on the process and organization of knowledge construction

Besides asking ‘What do we know?’ and ‘How do we know?’ Piaget’s epistemology proposes asking how we construct and develop knowledge from one level to a higher or lower level. This has been at the centre of some proposals of later applied sociocybernetics research (Amozurrutia, 2009; González, 2006; Maass et al., 2012) with the name of Ciberkultur@ and characterized as engaging Piaget’s genetic epistemology (1978, 2008, 2011).⁵ Ciberkultur@ is a sociocybernetics approach based on communication theory (Galindo, 1998, 2006; González et al., 2016) and applied technology for social innovation based on an alternative use of information and communication technologies, and has an important soft information systems component (Amozurrutia, 2011, 2018). It pays close attention to the collective experience of knowledge construction applied to PAR frameworks as it seeks to understand how people learn within frameworks of collective action. It uses concepts such as integration, differentiation and emergence to approach the process of knowledge construction.

Ciberkultur@ and PAR both emphasize the importance of the participants’ engagement in systematization and data analysis to achieve social transformation, and thus part of the objective of the research model is to increase their organizational capacity to generate information and knowledge on issues collectively identified as relevant. As a theoretical perspective, Ciberkultur@ addresses information and communication culture as a fundamental cognitive dimension of group development. Although these concepts may be difficult to grasp in practical terms, this participatory framework, developed as a part of sociocybernetics, seeks to integrate its observation and reflection within collective practices developed in the PAR context. These might be didactic activities to discuss what the data/information means for the participants and how they deal with it in their daily life, or data/information-gathering and organization where this is necessary for a deeper understanding of a situation in order to define observables about the social process under analysis.

An important distinction of this approach is its emphasis on integrating groups of participants with a degree of diversity in order to develop the research process. The group of local actors involved in projects is called the *emergent local knowledge community* (ELKC), and the interdisciplinary research group working on the project is called the *interdisciplinary research community* (IRC). These two distinctions emphasize the heterogeneity of both communities and the new levels of integration derived from the interrelated work while doing PAR; this approach underlines diversity as the strength of such groups, however it acknowledges the complexity to reach a common research goal. PAR is a complex process in itself, engaging multiple agents with heterogeneous approaches to knowledge construction. Ciberkultur@ develops analytical models based on information systems built by the different participants – a feature that has been

Figure 1. Elements of the PAR system.

integrated into the analytical model proposed here (Amozurrutia, 2009, 2011, 2018; González, 2003). The participants fully engage in the generation and analysis of the data and the definition of actions based on the information obtained (Almaguer-Kalixto, 2013). Sociocybernetics uses modelling methodologies to include information processing, cognition and system analysis. While computer simulation is at the core of systems science, sociocybernetics also includes soft systems methodology (Wilson and Van Haperen, 2015) to represent the research process (Amozurrutia, 2018).

Criteria for a participatory action research model based on sociocybernetics

In this section we propose the basis of an analytical PAR model using sociocybernetics concepts and methods including the elements discussed in the sections above (see Figure 1). The model is credible due to the intersection of the approaches, themes and interests of each framework. Both perspectives acknowledge the need for reflection on the problem at different levels, and for a systems perspective to address the research problems identified. They assume a heuristic strategy which takes the subjectivity of the actors into account.

PAR integrates a critical approach, with involvement in the specific context of the community/group, and emphasizes the importance of analysing the historical and social

Figure 2. From common elements to system features.

structure of the problem to be analysed (Fals-Borda et al., 1972). Few analytical tools exist that can derive a systemic explanation of such interactions. We consider that these features can be reinforced by integrating concepts of genetic epistemology to explain the cognitive structuration that occurs within the process (Amozurrutia, 2011; García, 2000; Piaget, 1978, 2013).

Another aspect common to both perspectives is their acknowledgement of subjectivity and complexity. PAR emphasizes participant subjectivity and its influence on the process; sociocybernetics uses the concept of the observer’s reflexivity and second-order reflexivity to address the situation in which the actor or participant observes and reflects on the process in which s/he is participating, or a further observer observes such participation, creating a reflection of it. While PAR defines complexity according to the interrelations of the participants, sociocybernetics addresses complexity in terms of the levels of interactions among the subsystems of which it is composed. We propose the following elements for the analytical model (Figure 2).

Figure 3 presents the features of the PAR system, integrating the aspects of each framework.

A model enhancing PAR for social intervention: Reflections from a case implementing the model

PAR system definition

The proposed model was implemented in a participatory research project which was part of a strategy of development projects launched in the Imlil Valley in the High Atlas region of Morocco by the local associations Imlil Valley Association (ABI, its French

Figure 3. New PAR system: integration of analytical categories.

abbreviation for Association Bassin d’Imlil) and the Association of Mountain Women (ATN, for Association Tamghart Noudrar) in collaboration with the Spanish NGO Centre for Rural Studies and International Agriculture (CERAI). Although the development project started in 2006,⁶ the PAR project began in October 2012 with the aim of promoting the recovery of Imlil collective memory and to understand the impact of the associations in the valley development. The partners agreed to take part in a PAR, using the model presented below. We started the first cycle following the process shown in Figure 4.

The cycle of the system’s definition/delimitation is oriented to identifying the research problem to be studied via the PAR system. The PAR system begins with the integration of two different groups: people interested in participating in a specific local context, organized as an Emergent Local Knowledge Community,⁷ and an Interdisciplinary Research Group.⁸ In this case the local group was composed of male and female members of the

Figure 4. PAR system definition cycle.

Imlil associations ABI and ATN. After sharing the implications of a participatory and systemic project and explaining its elements, we decided to set up a PAR project by identifying a collective research question altogether: how can we understand the role of civil society in the local development of Imlil? What new contributions can they bring to the valley?

The first cycle focused on activities for both groups together, such as planning reunions with participants and structured meetings with more orientation to PAR training. These first encounters were intended to stimulate interaction among the members that would create and reinforce their empathy and mutual trust, commitment and interest in the project to be addressed. The goal was to move from individual ideas to statements of the problem identified by all participants.

From a sociocybernetics point of view, at this stage attention should be paid to using a common language to enhance the collective understanding of the main concepts employed in the project: information, communication, knowledge, feedback, the system, observation, etc. Although some may have found these abstract concepts difficult to grasp, both groups needed at least a minimum of understanding of these categories to be able to communicate about them effectively. In this case, a two-day workshop on PAR and systemic approaches was held with the participants in French and Amazigh.⁹ Material support with examples from daily life helped to facilitate understanding and enable participation at these early stages.

After an exchange of ideas about this work done by the partnered groups, the local organizations expressed how they found it very difficult to address the history of civil

society work in the valley without including the social and natural environment of Imlil – in what appeared to be recognition of the influence of the contextual elements on the ‘internal’ parts of the system to be studied. In the case of the Imlil Valley it was the flooding of 1995 which resulted in dozens of deaths and revealed the inhabitants’ vulnerability, lack of support and poverty (Johnstone, 1997). The Bassin d’Imlil organization was created by family heads and traditional social structures such as the elders men council, also called *J'maaa*, with the objective of receiving and channelling help for the inhabitants of the valley after the flooding. The women’s organization was created after the flood on the initiative of women in situations of great economic vulnerability such as widowhood and divorce to help the women of the valley with literacy strategies, training for work and social integration.

Despite the fact that the formal origins of both organizations are similar in relation to overcoming social difficulties, the interrelations between them are difficult in a context of growing traditionalism and customs that undervalue mixed-sex interactions and the participation of women in economic activities.¹⁰

After reflecting on their origins and the importance of context in their constitutions and interactions, the local group decided to orientate the PAR project on the history, traditions and local customs of the valley. They saw this as a matter of great importance, because such knowledge was not written anywhere and resided mostly in the elders’ memories; younger generations, and particularly new inhabitants of the valley coming from other parts of Morocco were unaware of it. Visitors viewed Imlil town and the Imlil Valley as merely a crossroads that continues to Mt Toubkal, the second-largest mountain in Africa, and knew nothing of the local history and key facts.

Second cycle/subsystem: Project development

The second cycle involves implementation and development of the project, during which relationships among the actors are strengthened and new ones are created (Figure 5). The proposed action and follow-up strategies were defined from the list of problems identified and prioritized during the first cycle. The Ciberkultur@ framework emphasizes defining activities in which participants can observe their learning by doing. In the sociocybernetics approach this is a first-level observation. All participants, both local actors and researchers, observe their own actions and those of others during the research process and note how this iterative process modifies the research itself.

The importance of the shared knowledge defined in the first cycle led us to propose a deepening of local knowledge of the valley and its people and their ways of life and traditions. The majority of local participants were members of the three local organizations, and therefore the project had a high interdisciplinary and intercultural component. An effort at communication was needed, not only between those of different cultures but also between those speaking different languages. Most of the meetings included translation from Amazigh and Arabic to French and vice versa to ensure the local people’s participation and understanding.

The steps included here defined the research questions, the data to be collected and the methodological strategy for gathering and organizing information. Chávez

Figure 5. PAR analytical system: Second-cycle structure with analytical categories.

Méndez and Daza (2003) point out the importance of paying special attention to the systematization and evaluation of records, descriptions of the processes, and workshop conclusions produced during the project. Once the participants have engaged in a few cycles of production and revision there is an improvement in the overall process.

An example of this was the organization of mixed groups of researchers and local participants: one to identify topics to research from the collective meetings we had held and secondary and primary sources of information; another to use the first group’s results to propose the research activities; and a third group to design and implement a strategy for the defined activities. A series of questions was prepared to gather information about the village through interviews, especially with elderly people who had agreed to be interviewed by the local participants.¹¹ Another line of research was to retrieve information from festivities, traditions and local institutions: schools, the health clinic, the police, the guides’ office.

The output from this stage was the analysed information. Local participants engaged in the production of an information sheet on which they systematized the interviews, book reviews and media information. Forty data sheets were produced, each referring to a specific topic such as agriculture, infrastructure, traditions, etc. After the data collection the information was organized and a collective analysis was carried out. It is important the findings are interpreted collectively in order to outline the relevant outcomes and feed them back into the overall research process.

Figure 6. PAR analytical system: Third-cycle structure with analytical categories.

Third cycle/subsystem: PAR system observation

At the most practical level of this cycle decisions were taken about what to do with the information generated (Figure 6). The research results were translated into materials for dissemination according to the needs of the local group and others who can benefit from the experience in their own, different locations. This translation and use of the new knowledge relied on the local community's decisions and priorities because it required appropriation of their knowledge. This opened up a new stage of broader thinking and the use of communication skills, understanding that the product of the research now needed to be communicated to the context.

A report was generated for ABI, ATN and CERAI's internal analysis and joint cooperation. Information had been obtained on the past and present of Imlil and the valley, and on the role of the associations in local development, taking into account aspects such as local geography, infrastructure, the population's health and education and the predominant economic activities, including agriculture and tourism. The condition of women and social development cross-cut all of these data. Information already known and important information that remained to be investigated about the selected topics were identified: information about the past, the present, and the role of civil society in local development.

A book relating the history of Imlil as told by its inhabitants, participants in the project and testimonies recovered from other sources, entitled *Imlil selon ses habitants*, was published in an edition that integrated both Arabic and French. The book was produced together with the local participants deciding the texts, images and sections. The group decided together how they would distribute and promote the first edition. As the information was captured and organized using computing information systems it may be available for a second edition to include new information as time passes, and is available for the local organizations to edit by adding new information and further observations on the written facts or, as a complementary activity, to reinforce their sustainable tourism activities.

Conclusions

As mentioned above, the value that sociocybernetics adds to social science may be the comprehension of processes of change through the assimilation, accommodation and adaptation of the components and limits of the system, the feedback process and other interactions within the system and its environment, in order to analyse how social changes occur in complex settings. The paradigm is compatible with social study methods that prioritize reflexivity. In this way sociocybernetics may provide the conceptual paradigm for methods that promote the reflexivity process – among them, PAR.

In this case study the greatest challenge was putting this methodology into practice in the context of rural areas in Morocco characterized by a very traditional religious and cultural environment of patriarchal social organization. Implementing projects of this nature breaks down the gender barrier and allows the integration of men and women into working groups to exchange ideas and reflections as equals as a result of imagining a change to women's potential for participation in the making of collective decisions. The whole process, as explained to the local participants, was adapted to its specific context, respecting their social codes but showing the potential for building new collective social knowledge.

Sociocybernetics in particular emphasizes the aspect of change and seeks to show and explain how it occurs in systems. This enables one to understand the research in relationship to larger systems which are part of the contextual framework. Interrelations among elements and subsystems enable emergent actions to occur, which is important in PAR. We consider, however, that the most important contribution of sociocybernetics to PAR is second-order observation, as it emphasizes the role of the observer and offers a new opportunity to make PAR systemically reflective. If PAR is designed to understand – by generating knowledge – and transform aspects of social reality, it requires understanding of the structural conditions that have made its current status possible, the elements defined as parts of the system to be changed and acted upon, and the relations required to implement changes within.

PAR is a complex system inasmuch as it is a process that can be understood as a totality of relationships with a final purpose or objective. A series of heterogeneous components are also involved in this process, fulfilling specific functions in the system and organized in different degrees of relationships and interdependencies. As García (2006) states, like any other complex system the research system is surrounded by other

contextual elements found in the environment that irritate the active research system to a greater or lesser extent.

This article contributes a framework that, being consistent within sociocybernetics, can yet offer a bridge to other sociological analytical frameworks and other interdisciplinary research perspectives. By using the model in a case of PAR in the context of Imlil Valley in the High Atlas in Morocco we were able to systematize a complex research process – complex due not only to the heterogeneity of its participants and methodological openness but also to its cultural, political and economic context – rural communities with living under difficult conditions in Morocco’s High Atlas. It enabled us to understand and propose a research strategy for reaching the objectives by integrating cultural diverse working groups to exchange ideas and reflections in equal conditions, and to change women’s potential for participation in making collective decisions, on the research process and outcomes. In the context of rural Morocco, this is a feature to highlight. The systematization of the process enables a second-order observation, for other researchers beyond the first-order participants to analyse the process and offer feedback to improve the methodological proposal and its results.

Sociocybernetics is a conceptual framework that still has much to contribute to the sociological analysis of complex problems. Throughout this article we have presented the potential for it to contribute to other ISA research to enrich different sociological perspectives for better understanding and analysis of complex social problems. We have discussed the advantages of applying sociocybernetics in an advanced study using participatory action research, giving the example of the application of ideas drawn from sociocybernetics, which may be used in different social systems. We consider the model innovative, with a strong potential for application to social studies.

The task now is to enter into a stage of dialogue with other areas of sociology and other disciplines, with which we can build a complex system that can address the analysis of social problems and intervention strategies. It is important to value the path travelled up to now, but above all we urgently need to imagine strategies for future analysis scenarios that will combine systems thinking with second-order observation to promote reflective and more self-organized (autopoietic) social communities through collective action and research.

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Notes

1. We recommend the special issue of *Current Sociology*, Volume 60 Issue 2, March 2012, linking participatory research and action in practice. Also the SAGE Research Methods collection has an extensive selection of materials related to action research theory and practice at <https://methods.sagepub.com/>

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2. See in particular the articles in this issue by Bernd Hornung ('The challenges for sociocybernetics') and Bernard Scott ('The sociocybernetics of observation and reflexivity').
 3. Our translation from Spanish.
 4. As Geyer (1995: 12) mentions, it 'is more interested in morphogenesis and positive feedback loops than in homeostasis and negative feedback loops'.
 5. Piaget's genetic epistemology (1969, 1978, 2008, 2011) substantively incorporates empirical research into establishing the process of construction of knowledge, from birth and the most elementary forms of knowledge construction in childhood to the constitution of logical-mathematical structures. Through reflection based on his empirical findings, Piaget demonstrates the principle of the functional continuity of the constructive process on which he bases a general theory of knowledge (Garcia, 2000: 47).
 6. These projects aim to strengthen the development of the productive capacity and infrastructure of the Imlil Valley (irrigation channels, retaining walls, associative work space) and rural women's capacity through literacy, professional training and the integration of woman in productive activities.
 7. Name of local participants: Fatima Amrhan, Samira Errhioui, Zineb Laassri, Fatima Youzaline, Abdeslam Aztat, Mohamed Aziam, M. Ait Rami, Mustapha Aziam, Hadj Brahim, Aziam, Hassan Bouidbaden, Hadj Brahim Aziam, Hassan Bouidbaden, Fatima Bouabdi, Hadj Omar Ait Bahmed (Hadj Maurice), Malika Ait Idar, Abdessalam Aztat.
 8. Name of researchers: Eburne Caballero, Oussama Chakkor, Hasna Oujamaa, Rocio Tapiador, Roberto Higuero, Marisol Hübner, Laura Darphin, Víctor Herrera, Pedro J. Escriche y Patricia E. Almaguer-Kalixto.
 9. Amazigh is the local language of ethnic groups of Morocco and other countries of North Africa which are called Berber.
 10. The work carried out by CERAI in the Imlil Valley, however, increased as a requirement the participation of both organizations to facilitate projects and have an impact on women's development.
 11. Names of participants. Principally members of the J'mmaa.

ORCID iD

Patricia E Almaguer-Kalixto <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5944-7278>

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